

Multidisciplinary projects for Engineering, Business Administration and Design programs: Construction and mapping of common skills through an analysis instrument

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Abstract

In Brazil the Engineering, Business Administration and Design courses have, each one of them, a list of own competences, or skills, that are established on the curricular guidelines by Ministry of Education, to be developed by students along the course. This is not a closed list, and specific competences attending specific courses demands can be included, in order to training students with innovative and current profile. The engineering courses guidelines point out that students need to be trained with active learning strategies putting them as protagonists of their training and, besides this, courses need to make use of projects to develop the soft skills desirable in this training. To achieve an integrative approach, an institution created a new curriculum in which the students of these three courses interact in multidisciplinary projects. This approach has with bases the innovation tripod supporting the collaboration of the students of these three courses, aiming training them to a global scenario that claims professional's broad vision. Each multidisciplinary project is developed in an academic semester and the students need to enrol in two projects per semester. In this context emerged the need of a convergent list of competences that translate the competences of these three courses, without lose the essence of each one. This paper presents the process of building this unique list of competences, for training professionals with an updated and innovative profile. From this, a survey was carried out to gather information on the competences developed in these projects. The research method was the documental analysis for the creation of the list of competences. To survey the competences that are offered in the projects, a questionnaire sent to the instructors was used. The list of competences allowed the creation of an activity plan, in which they declare the competences that will be developed by students, ensuring the management of the learning process.

Keywords: Problem Based Learning; Competences; Multidisciplinary projects; Innovation tripod; Soft skills.

1 Introduction

The Engineering, Design and Business Administration courses at a higher education institution in Brazil have in common the use of projects that are offered to students throughout the course and in parallel to the subjects in the curriculum. These projects are "packaged" in a discipline called PAE (*Projetos e Atividades Especiais*, in English, Special Projects and Activities) and thus meet the need to be placed as elements of the curriculum. In this discipline, a list of more than two hundred projects is offered to the students, who have to choose at least two in each academic semester (Mattasoglio Neto et al, 2019).

The focus of this paper is the competencies that these projects allow be developed by the students. These projects need to meet two different aims: strictly speaking, the projects must develop technical and transversal competences. At the same time the competencies developed must be aligned with those defined in the DCNs (*Diretrizes Curriculares Nacionais*, in English, National Curriculum Guidelines) for these courses, Engineering, Business, and Design, promulgated by the Ministry of Education (MEC, 2019), which are the courses in which these projects are developed.

The projects offered to the students have another important characteristic. The students from all three courses can enroll in any project, that is, there will be students with different profiles working together in the same project.

The question discussed in this work is: How can we identify and define the competencies that will be developed in each project whether at the same group, there are students from three different courses, with different profiles and who should develop specific competencies determined by the National Curriculum Guidelines of the Ministry of Education.

This work analyzes and compares the competences explored Engineering, Business and Design areas (MEC, 2004; MEC 2019; MEC 2020), investigating what is common and what is specific for each of these programs, seeking to arrive in a set of competences that are common to these diverse areas of activity. The importance of the study lies in the fact that entering the job market has become more demanding by the students, both because the technical knowledge as for more professional attitudes that are being achieved in the curricula at the start of the 21st century (MESQUITA et al, 2013).

To achieve this end, document analysis was used to compare the DCNs in order to identify which competences and areas require more exploration, verifying which competences are most demanded in these careers, seeking to promote the education of a professional with a profile with a broad vision that guarantees the solution of problems effectively and efficiently, mobilizing knowledge and abilities with an entrepreneurial and innovative professional attitude. In turn, it is desirable that the competences are aligned with the ONU's sustainable development objectives that are translated into the Grand Challenges Scholar Program (GCSP) (BOTELHO et al, 2020).

This nexialist vision (CHINALLI, 2013; SOUZA Jr, 2019a) focuses on the training of a professional with the ability to connect different types of knowledge, in a current context in which there is a rapid expansion of technologies in an interdisciplinary way, promoting new learning. In short, it is the professional capable of promoting the connection of the problem to the knowledge of several areas, ensuring its solution, that is, giving it nexus.

Nexialists are professionals who manage to make these "different" connections naturally, coherently organizing the relationships between different types of knowledge. Therefore, they differ from the general brain pattern of knowledge construction, they think "out of the box" as they say. They see connections where others do not, see the opposite, escape the linear thinking of the absolute majority of professionals and think in a systemic way (CHINALLI, 2013).

2 Methodology

The research method used in this work is a document analysis of the DCNs of the three courses. So, the competences of the engineering, business and design degrees were analyzed and compared. Based on this process, it was possible to generate a single framework as a result of this work. In addition, the transversal competences that could best be associated with these three areas were also sought from other sources, establishing a new set of common competences.

2.1 Study context

In the institution where the research was conducted, the "Innovation Tripod" (Souza Jr., 2019b), is used as a reference, for the connection between the knowledge of the Business, Design and Engineering areas (Figure 1). Aiming to explore this concept, the institution has the PAEs (Special Projects and Activities) as a tool to develop new competencies - both technical and transversal.

Figure 1 - Tripod of innovation at IMT (Souza Jr, 2019b)

The Figure 1 is about the union between these three courses, so that what is learned in one area can be used in the other two, for example, the business administration area that makes the products more viable for the consumption of a target audience (Viability), the design that can make this product aesthetically beautiful and functional (Desirability), and engineering that deals with the components and operation of the product (Feasibility). In general terms, the idea is to distribute these three great concepts so that, for example, an engineer also knows something related to design.

This structuring of the course with the introduction of PAEs provides an opportunity for interaction with current professionals working in the labor market, further increasing the richness of these experiences. It is worth pointing out that any professional from the Brazilian or foreign market can propose a PAEs, which, if there are students interested, can be offered and incorporated into the student's curriculum.

Based on the importance of these projects and on the needs and opportunities for the student's education, the projects can contribute to, by developing the desired competencies, generating an enrichment of the education, always based on the DCNs of the courses that guide the curricular planning of a discipline.

2.2 Data collection and analysis

The research developed had a few phases:

1st Step:

In this step, the focus was on the competences stated in the National Curriculum Guidelines for the three degree programs, Engineering, Business and Design. The method used in this work was document analysis in order to identify the competences that are intended to be developed in these degree programs. The competences of the three programs were compared in order to find similarities and differences between them. This comparison led to a single list that would cover all three degrees simultaneously.

2nd Step:

With the list of common competences, a survey instrument was designed, more precisely a questionnaire with the aim of identifying which competences would be declared in the projects offered in the PAEs in the first semester of 2022. This questionnaire was built and validated and structured in Google Forms, in order to facilitate data collection for the research that was to be developed.

3rd Step:

This step consisted of registering the projects that would be offered to students in the first semester of 2022. Each teacher or external professional who intended to offer a workshop or project as an PAE would have to fill out a form in Google forms, in which they would indicate what competencies they would develop for the students. The teachers need to detail some characteristics of the project for the registration of the activity, we

decided to make this registration online through a form and we took the opportunity to ask about the competences, in other words, they were required to answer the questions desired by the authors for the registration of the project, although other questions will be asked, the main focus will be on the competencies part, the vast majority were for the registration of the activity itself.

Once these three steps were completed, the data from step 3 was synthesized in an Excel spreadsheet, which allowed for its analysis.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Development

In practical terms, was separated and analyzed the eight DCNs for Engineering. Subsequently, the DCNs for Business and then the DCNs for Design were together analyzed again. The initial idea was to create a common list of 8 competences based on the Engineering DCNs, but one detail led to the appearance of more categories of competences: an engineering competence did not always have a corresponding one for other courses, or vice versa. This meant that some items in the common competency block had no connection to the 3 courses in the DCNs. However, because some of them are related in a practical way, they are in the Common Competencies block. The result was a single block with 10 competencies.

The transversal competences is a common block of 10 competences was also arrived at for the transversal competences, which were taken from some work in the area of Engineering Education (MESQUITA et al, 2013, MATTA, et al, 2018).

Summarizing, the technical competences and the transversal competences were indicated in the list of competences for the graduation programs.

3.2 The competences list

The list of competences considered for the questionnaire is:

Transversal Competences:

- **Critical Sense (Be Critical)** - The idea is for the student to have a notion of what is tolerable or not even before solving an exercise or problem, for example. This means that the student will have a dexterity to solve challenges in a certain area of knowledge, in addition to knowing whether the values and answers found are acceptable and correct.
- **Information Selection (Be Selective)** - To solve a project, an assignment, or something else, one often needs to consult sources for help, be it the teacher, recommended books, or the subject matter itself and this competence is responsible for selecting this information.
- **Knowing how to face challenges** - When it comes to real world problems, it is important that the professional knows how to face these problems, it is important that the individual is courageous and has solution attitudes, in some circumstances, it is necessary that the student has a solid opinion, a solution and has the courage to introduce it to his environment.
- **Proactivity (Initiative)** - It is the ability to anticipate and responsibly target attitudes on imposed occasions before they even happen.
- **Create / Innovate** - The ability to create products, assets, services (among others) in an innovative and creative way, that is, to produce something useful, necessary, and new.
- **Organization / Planning** - Produce and act in an organized and planned way.
- **Interpersonal relationship** - Being empathetic and agreeable, that is, thinking of others working together, acting fully, and making decisions thinking of the whole.
- **Ability to deal with the unforeseen / Working in uncertain environments** - The student's ability to deal with problems rationally and calmly, to adapt to change, to withstand various pressures imposed by the environment, and to overcome obstacles, basically resilience.
- **Ability to solve problems** - Be effective at solving problems.
- **Make decisions** - Be decisive and take harsh and determined attitudes.

Technical Competences:

- To formulate and design desirable and innovative solutions in your area.
- To analyze and understand the phenomena, events and models in your area based on the sciences that underlie it.
- Creatively conceive, design and analyze systems, products (goods and services), components or processes, technically and economically viable.
- Implement, oversee and control solutions in your area.
- Communicate effectively in written, oral and graphic forms, including communication in LIBRAS.
- Working and leading multidisciplinary teams
- Know and ethically apply the legislation and normative acts within the scope of the exercise of the profession.
- Learn autonomously and deal with new and/or complex situations and contexts.
- Understand the potential of technologies and apply them in solving problems and taking advantage of opportunities.
- Get to know the productive sector of your specialization, revealing a solid sectorial view, related to the market, materials, production processes and technologies.

3.3 Survey Development

A questionnaire was created with a list of competencies, as well as other data used in the internal record of the projects themselves. The importance of having this questionnaire is the easy access to the data and its analysis in digital form.

Among the questions presented were "Has this PAE been offered sometime?", to give us control over which ones had already been offered during and before the pandemic, "Choose your PAE category", giving the person answering a list, making them choose among several areas, and the questions referring to the competencies, where we put the two lists, each one as a question, and asked the teachers to choose a maximum of 3, in the case of the transversal competencies, the respondent could choose none, but this was not the case with any of the answers. In the technical competences analyzed, it was mandatory to choose at least one competence.

3.4 The questionnaire results

The data from the questionnaire are presented in the following.

Figure 2 - Has this project already been offered?

It is worth noting that PAEs have existed at Mauá since 2015, and even after almost 7 years, there is always a high demand for new PAEs, which is the case as more than 30% of these activities offered are new this semester. This provides current and ever-renewing learning

Figure 3 - Are you already an instructor at IMT?

Some PAEs instructors are professionals in the job market, and they do not work as teachers in the institution. Therefore, we asked them about their origin, and we can see in Figure 3 - Are you already an instructor at IMT? that almost 43% of the instructors who apply the PAEs are not professors, that is, they are professionals in the job market. This is an interesting fact, as it creates an experience and a new window of opportunity with even more qualified teachers.

Figure 4 - Transversal competences analyzed

Label:

- I – Critical Sense - Be Critical
- II - Information Selection - Be Selective
- III - Knowing how to face challenges

- IV - Proactivity - Initiative
- V - Create / Innovate
- VI - Organization / Planning
- VII - Interpersonal relationship
- VIII - Ability to deal with the unforeseen / Working in uncertain environments
- IX - Ability to solve problems
- X - Take decisions

It can be seen that among the transversal competences analysed, those that stood out most were those related to problem-solving competences, which shows that the projects always have a "hands-on" idea, in other words, being able to solve real-world problems. Next is the competence to create and innovate, which was also expected to receive a high number of responses, since most projects have the idea of creating a professional with new and effective resolutions. In general, it is possible to see that all competencies were met to some extent, most of the questionnaires had 3 competencies, and in this question it was not even required to select an item. With this data, we can see that this list of transversal competencies was satisfied.

Figure 5 - Technical competences analyzed

Label:

- I - To formulate and design desirable and innovative solutions in your area.
- II - To analyze and understand the phenomena, events and models in your area based on the sciences that underlie it.
- III - Creatively conceive, design and analyze systems, products (goods and services), components or processes, technically and economically viable.
- IV - Implement, oversee and control solutions in your area.
- V - Communicate effectively in written, oral and graphic forms, including communication in LIBRAS.
- VI - Working and leading multidisciplinary teams.

VII - Know and ethically apply the legislation and normative acts within the scope of the exercise of the profession.

VIII - Learn autonomously and deal with new and/or complex situations and contexts.

IX - Understand the potential of technologies and apply them in solving problems and taking advantage of opportunities.

X - Get to know the productive sector of your specialization, revealing a solid sectorial view, related to the market, materials, production processes and technologies.

In relation to these technical competences analyzed, was tried to see, as compactly as possible, the integration of Engineering, Business and Design. The answers allows to see that all of them are fulfilled. One can see that some were highlighted, especially those related to the formulation and conception of desirable solutions (I) and design and analyze solutions technically and economically viable (III), that is, once again, the issue of the "creative mind".

The Figure 5 also shows what was expected about the projects having "technical" competences to be developed. An important detail is that even the least explored competences are still a high number in relation to the total: practically 8.3% of the projects have the objective of knowing and ethically applying legislation and normative acts within the scope of professional practice (VII).

In a practical way, for example competence VII, which was the least answered, if from these 15 answers about 20 classes are opened, since the same activity can have more than one timetable depending on student demand, at least 350 students will be reached if these classes are opened, since the activities have about 20 students per class, that is a small demonstration that this "15" is still a very large number and that it can reach a considerable number of students.

Table 1 - PAEs Category

Category Name	Number of answers
Industrial Management	1
Mockups and modeling	1
Citizenship	2
Exact sciences	3
Energy	3
Expression & Imaging	3
Hardware & Embedded Systems	3
Games	3
Robotics & Automation	3
Materials	4
Simulation and computational optimization	4
Cities and urban solutions	5
Data Science	5
Academic competitions	5
Finance	6
Careers	8
Environment and Sustainability	8
Applied sciences	9
Management skills	10
Entrepreneurship	12
Product research and development	12
Engineering solutions	12
Industrial projects and processes	16
Development of socioemotional skills	17
Software training	26

The categories indicate to which area the offered project is directed. The idea is that these projects should be diverse, since we are looking for a nexialist profile and, in this sense, the more areas students are offered, the more versatile they can become. As it is an institution with a strong emphasis on Technology, it is natural to have more courses related to software training.

4 Conclusion

The aim of this work was to create a common list of competences for Engineering, Business and Design programs, so that the competences declared by instructors of projects offered to students from these three courses can be surveyed. The importance of this common list lies in the fact that students from these three courses can enroll and participate in these projects and having a common standard of competences helps in identifying what is being taught in these projects.

The most important initial conclusion is that it was possible to construct this single list, which was validated and allows the identification of common competences among these three courses. A second conclusion is that it was possible to construct a data collection instrument on the projects that allows the instructor to state which competences he intends to develop in the students. The third conclusion was a quantitative survey that allows us to know which competences are being developed in the projects.

All of this allows for a management of the projects offered to students. In this way, it is possible to act so that competencies that appear little in the projects offered to students are encouraged, in order to cover any gaps. This allows a broad vision that helps in the management of the institution's courses.

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